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Modernism: A Critical Perspective

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Abstract:

The present paper analyses the textuality and historicity of modernism in detail. The history of critical theory is marked by major theoretical upheavals that have changed paradigm of literature and critical theory. Modernism, being inspired by radicalism of the Enlightenment, attempts to bring revolutionary change not only literature but also in the society. Most significantly, it aims to decenter the center and centralize the margin in the domain of discourse. Conceptually speaking, the modernity of modernism is a logical synthesis of progressive vision of emancipatory forces.

Keywords: Textuality, historicity, critical theory, Enlightenment, radicalism. revolutionary change.

Modernism, in the sphere of literary and non-literary world, was an epoch-making 'artistic or cultural phenomena' (Simon Malpas:9) which had changed the course of the human history. Philosophically speaking, the spirit of modernism was marked by urge to 'make it new' (Ezra Pound:) in the conceptual framework and experimentation in methodology of the representation. For some writers and critics, modernism was the revolutionary movement

which was trying to liberate the humanity from the bondage of the tradition. On the contrary, modernism was the degradation and decline of the mighty European civilization for some writers and critics. Modernism, for poet like Ezra Pound, was basically 'a vision of European decay' (Christopher Butler:47). Though modernism was originated and developed as European phenomena, it also reached the native shores, bringing the radical energy to uproot the dominant structures of the governance.

Modernism did not take place in vacuum but it was the effect of social changes in the contemporary society. Simon Malpas argues,

The modern begins with the transformation of European culture during the Renaissance, which saw the rise of capitalism, the spread of Protestantism and beginning of a deconstruction of feudal hierarchies. (Simon Malpas:9)

The European society, since the days of Renaissance, was going through the great phase of the transformation which was effected by the victory of the rationality over irrationality which was ruling ideology of the medieval era. Based on the scientific vigor of the rationality, there was spread of science and scientific temper in the post-Renaissance Europe which had liberated it from the dominance of the dark ages of the medievalism. Due to the application of science and scientific vision, there was the development of the industrial revolution in Europe in which manual labor was replaced by the machine labor. Given that the industrial revolution made revolutionary changes in the system of means of production, there were tectonic changes in the social relations and power patterns in the society. Before the French revolution, the intellectuals prepared the ground for the success of the revolution. Similarly, before the development of modernism as the progressive movement, thinkers had played a very important role in the making of the social atmosphere for the flowering of the modernism. M. H.

Abrahams, in his famous book, *Glossary of the Literary Terms* pointed out the contribution of the intellectuals. He argues,

Important intellectual precursors of modernism, in this sense, are thinkers who had questioned the certainties that had supported traditional modes of social organisation, religion, and morality, and also traditional ways of conceiving the human self – thinkers such as Friedrich Nietzsche (1844-1900), Karl Marx, Sigmund Freud and James G. Frazer. (M. H. Abrahams: 167)

As the history of world shows, the individual as the subject of discourse, was always shackled by the dominant structures before the coming of the modernism. Conceptually speaking, the social analysis of class conflict, by Karl Marx, had changed not only social system but also the way in which literary aesthetics was consumed. Like the theory of Marxism, which has challenged the conventional understanding and knowledge, the psychoanalytical theory by Freud has revolutionized `` not only the field of psychology but also of the literature. Based on the heterogenous and radical theories of Marxism and psychoanalysis, modernism has become very famous for its diversity and the revolutionary energy which had envisioned a brave new world for the victims of dominant structures. Due to radicalism of the modernism, there was a creative and critical urge to venture beyond the theoretical and structural limitations which were set by traditional orthodoxy who were part of patronage of power structure of the contemporary age.

The most important feature of modernism is its progressive vision which has imagined a better world rather than existent world which is marked by ceaseless conflicts. As the ‘modern movement as only a detour or dead end away from the main highway of tradition’ (Maurice Bee-1066), it is greatly inspired by the emancipatory spirit of the Marxism. In his famous essay, ‘What is Author’ (2008), Foucault placed Marx and Freud as ‘founders of

discursivity' (Foucault:911), for their new experimentation in the area of the discourse.

Foucault argues,

Freud is not just the author of *The Interpretations of Dreams or Jokes and Theirs Relation to the Unconscious*; Marx is not just author of the *Communist Manifesto* or *Capital*: they both have established an endless possibility of discourse. These founders of discursivity have produced something else: the possibilities and rules for the formation of other texts. ((Foucault:911)

Though the working-class movements were originated and developed in 19th century, it is in the heyday of modernism in which the working class managed to hold the power in different countries. Historically speaking, T.S. Eliot's *The Waste Land* (1922), which is regarded as the most representative text of the modernism, was published after the Bolshevik revolution in 1917 in Russia. As the traditional methods of literary representation failed to express 'the immense panorama of futility and anarchy which is contemporary history' (T.S. Eliot), similarly the traditional politics failed to offer radical solutions to the problems of working class. Comparatively speaking, if modernism employed literary experimentation by using new forms and new subject matter to develop new literary aesthetics, similarly Marxism deployed political innovation by using new methods of political organization and ideology to acquire the state power to develop the welfare state. Though modernism was a kind of decadence for the western imagination, modernism was very empowering phenomena for the third world countries which were victim of the colonial domination. Under the combined influence of modernism and Marxism, the nationalism in such colonized countries got some kind of progressive character which was very different from narrow minded racial nationalism of the colonial authority. Based on the radicalism of Marxism and modernism, the political movement of decolonization actually played very important role in the demise of the colonial empire. 'Given the pluralism and dissent that characterizes this period' (Christopher Butler:26),

modernism had uncanny similarities with Marxism due to its inherent belief that ‘literature is not a surrogate for religion’ (Cleanth Brooks :798). In simple words, modernism was trying to develop the new vocabulary to express the new complex reality of the contemporary age.

Like the movement of Enlightenment which is famous for its inclusive approach and emancipatory vision, modernism is credited for the creation of the socialist alternative to the ‘capitalist universality’. Conceptually speaking, modernism involves ‘a deliberate and radical break with some of the traditional bases not only of Western art, but of Western culture in general (M. H. Abrahams :167). Due to its rejection of ethnocentric approach and outlook of traditional literary discourse, modernism adopts revolutionary approach in the choice of the literary forms and subjects. By giving importance to the plurality and dissent, modernism has broken the hold of powerful dominant social, political, and literary structures and created the new values which are relevant to changed material conditions of the contemporary age.

The modern literature, due to its diversity and heterogeneity, includes literary forms like the social realism and critical theory like Marxism. During the regime of Stalin, though social realism was degenerated into the vulgar Marxism, still social realism managed to express the voice of voiceless in the fictional world. Most significantly, the Marxist school of criticism, through use of the trope of the economic determinism, highlighted the role of material forces while shaping of the ideological elements. Leon Trotsky (1879-1940), the Russian revolutionary and critic, in his essay ‘Literature and Revolution’, pointed out the positive role played by the Marxism. He argues,

It is very true that one cannot always go by the principles of Marxism in deciding whether to reject or accept a work of art. A work of art should, in the first place, be judged by its own law, that is, by the law of art. But Marxism

alone can explain why and how a given tendency in art has originated in a given period of history. (Leon Trotsky:178).

Due to the diverse elements such as Marxism, modernism is very different from the other literary movements. Most significantly, this synthesis of modernism and Marxism has made modernism as the progressive phenomenon. In the British literature, W. H. Auden, G. B. Shaw were influenced by the ideas of Marxism. In their literary output, one can observe a fine blending of Marxism and modernism. Even in the Indian context, writers like Premchand, Mulk Raj Anand were deploying Marxist content in the modernist forms. For example, Mulk Raj Anand's novel *The Untouchable* (1935) is the good example of combination of Marxist content and modernist form. Based on the radicalism of Marxism, Progressive Writers' Association tried to fuse socialist values in modern forms of the narration. In the development of Indian nationalism, such groups played a very crucial role. Due to the contribution of such groups, Indian nationalism developed its progressive character. In simple words, modernism and Marxism are complimentary to each other and both have played very important role in developing the meta narrative of resistance to the dominant power structures. Conceptually speaking, both are new types of hermeneutics which have galvanized the social system of signification. Developed from the same source of the Enlightenment, both movements dream about the liberation of the human subjectivity from the bondage of the dominant power structures. `

The liberating spirit of modernism was not limited only to the structure of the class but it also included the social structure of the gender. Along with class, modernism has also liberated the women from the clutches of the tradition. For the women and feminist writers, modernism was the progressive phenomena. Due to the revolutionary changes in medical science, the women have become successful in gaining control over their bodies. By rejecting

the Victorian idea of women as ‘angel in the house’, Modernism focused on the individualism of women rather than their collective identity under the tutelage of the patriarchy.

Comparatively speaking, modernism’s passion for the new forms, or its celebration of the autonomy of the art is also closely related to the women who were claiming their much-denied autonomy of the body under the protective wings of the modernism. Most significantly, the impressive thing about the dominant social structures is that they are in alliance with each other to exploit the marginal people across time and space. For the women, the alliance between religion, tradition and patriarchy was the mighty obstacle which was mostly responsible for the suppression of the women since time immortal. Being praised for its rejection of the traditional values and assumptions, modernism has also rejected the unholy alliance between the tradition, religion, and patriarchy to free women from their perpetual subjectification. Most significantly, this process of subjectification has ‘silenced’ and ‘othered’ women. Therefore, they are absent or invisible all time in the discourse. Virginia Woolf (1882-1941), in her essay *A Room of One’s Own* (1926), points out,

One knows nothing detailed, nothing perfectly true and substantial about her.
History scarcely mentions her. (Woolf:37)

Having internalized the patriarchy, women willingly participate in ‘the war of position’ as unknown or invisible victim. Actually ‘anonymity runs in their blood’ (Woolf:42), which is an outcome of manipulations of the discourse by the patriarchy. By rejecting the patriarchal modes of literary expression, production and consummation, modernism basically empowers the women to create an alternative mode of expression in the domain of literature. Due to the radical ethos and energy, feminist writers like Virginia Woolf could write independently without paying attention to dominant social structures. She argues,

A woman must have money and room of her own if she is to write fiction.

(Woolf:4)

Such kind of original and courageous analysis of discourse, it is generally believed, is only possible under the protective wings of modernism. Hence, modernism, in the domains of literature and material reality, has become a kind of savior for the women of the contemporary age.

Modernism has not only improved the social conditions of women in real life but also transformed the method of representation of women characters in literature. In the traditional literature, women were presented as the 'objects of the desire' or 'other' in the literary universe. As in the real life, women were given the secondary positions as compared to their male counterpoints in the literature also. Virginia Woolf argues,

A very queer, composite being thus emerges. Imaginatively she is of the highest importance; practically she is completely insignificant. She pervades poetry from cover to cover; She is all absent from history. She dominates the lives of kings and conquerors in fiction; in fact, she was the slave of any boy whose parents forced a ring upon her finger. Some of the most inspired words, some of the most profound thoughts in literature fall from her lips; in real life she could hardly read, could scarcely spell, and was the property of her husband.

(Woolf:36)

In the literary universe, they were just heroines like Ophelia but not as the protagonist Hamlet. Even the literary process of cannon making was not free from the manipulations of power games which denied women their due place not only in society but also in the discourse. Conceptually speaking, in the system of the literary production, only male writers like Homer, Horace, were regarded as 'great' or 'canonical' and even male characters like Achilles,

Ulysses, etc. were regarded as capable of the heroic action. Even female writers hide their real identity to get their works published. In the opinion of Virginia Woolf, women writers ‘sought ineffectively to veil themselves by using the name of a man.’ (Woolf:42).

As Marx rightly pointed out in his theory of means of production, women never controlled the means of production. According to Marxism, those who control means of production, control the discourse also. Hence, women never controlled discourse. Virginia Woolf argues,

Intellectual freedom depends upon material things. Poetry depends upon intellectual freedom. And women have always been poor, not for two hundred years merely, but from the beginning of time. Women have had less intellectual freedom than the sons of Athenian slaves. Women, then, have not had a dog’s chance of writing poetry. That is why I have laid so much stress on money and a room of one’s own. (Virginia Woolf: 90)

Conceptually speaking, modernism is an empowering phenomenon for the deprived sections of the society, be it women or the working class. By making individualism as foundation of new epoch, it has breathed liberating air into the modern society. Literature, as its anatomy shows, is always contextual and it faithfully records the age in which it is produced and consumed. Therefore, modern literature is radical, innovative and celebrates individualism. In short, modernism has ushered new creative and critical energy in the domain of the discourse.

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